

A list of 101 Supermassive Black Holes

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Abstract

It is now well established that Supermassive Black Holes (SMBHs) are present at the centre of many galaxies including our own. The masses of such SMBHs have been measured in nearby galaxies as well as in distant quasars. In this work we briefly review the most common current methods used to determine the mass of SMBHs and we present a list with a sample of 101 SMBHs hosted in different types of galaxies.

1 Introduction

The existence of SuperMassive Black Holes (SMBHs) at the centers of galaxies was suspected long before it was possible to accurately measure the masses of such objects. In the case of Active Galactic Nuclei (AGNs), Zeldovich (1964), Salpeter (1964), and Lynden-Bell (1969) concluded that AGNs are

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plausibly powered by gravitational infall onto supermassive collapsed objects [1, 2, 3, 4]. In the case of quiescent galaxies, it was suspected that M87 might harbor a $\sim 10^9 M_\odot$ Massive Dark Object (MDO) [5, 6].

The dynamical detection of MDOs in galaxy centers began in 1984 with the discovery of an $M_{MDO} \sim 10^{6.5} M_\odot$ mass in M32. In the following years MDOs were also detected at the centers of M31, NGC 4594 and NGC 3115. The observations were all ground-based with a resolution of $1''$. For more details see e.g. [7] and references therein.

Notice that it is not straightforward to conclude that an MDO is a SMBH. In fact a MDO could be a dark cluster formed by any plausible form of nonluminous gravitating objects (e.g. brown dwarfs, white dwarfs, neutron stars, stellar mass BHs, other species of very low mass objects). To argue convincingly that an MDO is a SMBH we must rule out all the other plausible alternatives [8]. In addition, although a SMBH which forms or grows in a galactic nucleus produces a cusp in the local stellar density, that is not enough evidence to ensure the presence of a SMBH (see [9] for a complete discussion). On the case of AGNs the short variability timescales observed in many of them place an upper bound on the size of the radiating region and, as far as we know the simplest way to generate large amounts of power in a very small volume is to accrete matter onto a SMBH [4].

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we review summarily some key aspects concerning the dynamic methods currently applied on the evaluation of the masses of SMBH present at the centers of quiescent galaxies and in Sections 3 and 4 we proceed, respectively, with the reverberation mapping method and the Fe II emission line method which are particularly useful in the case of AGNs. In Section 5 we review the scaling relation between SMBH masses and the bulge dispersion velocity. In Section 6 we present the main results of our work: a list with **101** SMBHs. Finally, in Section 7 we finish with some conclusions and remarks.

2 Dynamical Methods

The radius of influence of a SMBH is defined as the distance at which its potential significantly affects the orbital motions of stars or gas, with its value given by [4]:

$$r_{inf} = \frac{GM_\bullet}{\sigma^2} \tag{1}$$

where M_\bullet is the SMBH mass, σ is the velocity dispersion of the stars or gas within the galaxy bulge and G is the gravitational constant. Inside r_{inf} ,

stellar or gas dynamics are dominated by the presence of the SMBH, and dynamical measurements on this scale or smaller make it possible to measure the SMBH mass with some confidence [10]. It was only in the HST era that sufficient angular resolution to resolve r_{inf} was achieved [10]. In fact the HST provided spatial resolution a factor of 3 to 10 better than ground-based telescopes [7].

The dynamical signature imprinted by a SMBH on the motion of surrounding matter is unique. Within the sphere of influence, a Keplerian rotation or velocity dispersion of stars or gas is an unambiguous proof of the existence of a MDO [11]. Of course that at first a MDO could be either a SMBH or a dark cluster. Maoz (1998) [8] provided rough calculations of the lifetime of a dark cluster against evaporation and collapse. For any choice of the cluster's mass and density (or, equivalently, radius and density) such lifetime depends on the cluster's composition. Maoz (1998) considered the evolution of clusters made of brown dwarfs, white dwarfs, neutron stars and stellar mass black holes. The main argument is that when the observations imply densities and masses for which the dark cluster lifetime is short, if compared to the age of the host galaxy, then the case for a SMBH becomes more likely [11].

The SMBH mass evaluation methods based on dynamic or kinematic processes include [11]:

- Stellar Proper Motion (SPM)
- Stellar Dynamics (SD)
- Gas Dynamics (GD)
- Maser Dynamics (MD)

The case for a SMBH at the Galactic Center is a special one due to its proximity. In fact proper motions of the star cluster surrounding Sgr A* can be detected using near infrared imaging techniques. SPM has been measured for nearly 50 stars within our galactic centre. For some stars it was possible to trace accurate orbits with periods of the order of tens of years and pericenters of ~ 10 AU. This implies a central mass of $4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ and a central mass density of $4 \times 10^{16} M_{\odot} Mpc^{-3}$, providing evidence that the mass is indeed in the form of a SMBH [11].

Modeling the kinematics of stars in galactic nuclei has historically been the method of choice to constrain the central potential, and for good reasons: stars are always present, and their motion is always gravitational. However, stellar absorption lines are faint and the central surface brightness, especially

in bright ellipticals, is low. Acquiring good stellar kinematical data from SD studies is not always possible due to natural or technical reasons. Theoretical challenges arise from the fact that the stellar orbital structure is unknown and difficult to recover from the observables [11, 12].

GD mass measurements in principle offer several major advantages compared to SD modeling. The central few hundred parsecs of practically all spiral galaxies and $> 50\%$ of S0 and elliptical galaxies have detectable optical nebular line emission. From a practical point of view, nebular emission lines are much easier to measure than stellar absorption lines. Another appeal of using GD instead of SD lies in the conceptual simplicity of the modeling. If the gas is in Keplerian rotation in a dynamically cold disk, the analysis is vastly less intricate and computationally cheaper than the orbit-based machinery needed to treat the stars [12]. However it must be taken into account that gas, unlike stars, can easily be accelerated by non gravitational forces (e.g. magnetic fields) in which case it will be not possible to measure the SMBH mass due to the non-Keplerian motion [11].

Water masers can be produced when X-rays, generated by the innermost accretion disk around the central SMBH, illuminate and heat a torus of gas and dust around the central region. The model leads to a sandwich structure in which the high-pressure gas closest to the midplane is molecular but the lower-pressure gas above and below the plane is atomic. When the X-ray heating is large enough to raise the temperature in gas and dust above 400 K, but small enough to permit the existence of H_2 , a reaction network $O + H_2 \rightarrow OH + H$ and $OH + H_2 \rightarrow H_2O + H$ is very efficient at producing water with an abundance ratio of water to hydrogen of several 10^{-4} [11].

Emitting at 22 GHz, the masers can be studied with the VLBA at spatial resolutions a factor ~ 200 higher than can be achieved using the HST, instantly pushing the ability to detect a SMBH to correspondingly smaller masses [11]. However, H_2O masers are not common. This is not surprising, since to detect water masers the observer must see a long path length through the torus [11].

3 Reverberation Mapping

With the present day telescopes and spectrographs it is not feasible to spatially resolve the sphere of influence in galaxies that are farther than $z \approx 0.03$. In that cases the mass of the SMBH cannot be measured after SD, GD or MD measurements. A way to measure SMBH masses in more distant, quiescent galaxies or low luminosity AGNs has yet to be devised [11].

For some AGNs, however, an alternative technique is available. In fact the

Reverberation Mapping (RM) method targets the Broad Line Region (BLR) of Type 1 AGNs, probing material within only a few hundred Schwarzschild radii from the singularity, a factor 10^3 closer than the one that can be reached by SD or GD studies using HST [11].

According to the unification scheme of AGNs (see e.g. [4]), the central black hole and accretion disk are completely surrounded by an obscuring, geometrically thick molecular torus. The geometry and extent of the torus are dictated by the requirement that, to account for the well known polarization properties of Seyfert 1 and Seyfert 2 galaxies, the Broad Line Region (BLR) must be entirely enclosed within it, while the Narrow Line Region (NLR) - which extends from a few to several thousand parsecs - must be largely outside. The BLR extends from a few light days to several tens of light weeks from the central engine. Although a factor 10 to 100 times larger than the inner accretion disk, and three orders of magnitudes larger than the Schwarzschild radius of the SMBH the BLR remains spatially unresolved with present day instrumentation [11].

If assumptions are made regarding the geometry of the BLR, and it is assumed that the motion of the clouds is gravitational, then the binding mass can be rather trivially derived from the virial theorem [11]:

$$M = \frac{f r_{BLR} \sigma^2}{G} \quad (2)$$

where the mean velocity σ is given by the emission line width (given by the FWHM of the emission lines) and f is a factor or order unity which depends on the geometry and kinematics of the BLR [11]. The unknown geometry, kinematics, and inclination of the BLR ultimately limit the accuracy to which black hole masses can be determined [10].

The RM method is essentially based on Kepler's law applied, in this case, to the BLR. It requires long-term, careful monitoring of both continuum and broad emission lines, and it can only be applied to those AGNs in which the BLR is directly observable, namely Type 1 Seyferts and quasars [11]. The velocity of the matter in this region is estimated from the width of the $H\beta$ emission line and the distance r_{BLR} from the center which is given directly by the time delay of the variability of the emission from the BLR with respect to that from the central region [13]. With careful monitoring of the flux variability of the continuum and emission lines, we can measure this time delay, or lag, τ , between continuum and emission-line variations, and thus determine the size of the line-emitting region [10]:

$$r_{BLR} = c\tau \quad (3)$$

Observation shows a correlation of both the r_{BLR} and the central mass with continuum luminosity. There is a $r_{BLR} - L_\lambda$ relation where the BLR size (measured from the $H\beta$ broad lines) correlates with the monochromatic continuum luminosity, measured at 5100\AA , which is given by [11]:

$$r_{BLR} = 30.2 \times \left(\frac{\lambda L_\lambda(5100\text{\AA})}{10^{44} \text{ ergs}^{-1}} \right)^{0.66} \text{ (light days)} \quad (4)$$

Once the BLR size is known, the SMBH mass is easily derived from the virial relation [11]:

$$M_\bullet = 1.5 \times 10^5 \left(\frac{r_{BLR}}{\text{light days}} \right) \left(\frac{v}{\text{kms}^{-1}} \right)^2 M_\odot \quad (5)$$

valid under the assumption of isotropy for the BLR. Since both the radius r_{BLR} and the velocity (or equivalently the $H\beta$ width $\Delta\lambda$) were found empirically to scale with the total luminosity of the nucleus, the SMBH mass is given by [14]:

$$M_\bullet = 5.71 \times 10^7 \left(\frac{\lambda L_\lambda(5100\text{\AA})}{10^{44} \text{ ergs}^{-1}} \right)^{0.545} M_\odot \quad (6)$$

The RM method can be applied in the case of AGNs, where the previous methods (GD, SD, MD) cannot be used (the emission from the active nucleus over-shines the stellar component and the velocity dispersion which is based on stellar absorption lines cannot be determined).

An important advantage related to the RM method is that the region probed is only a factor 1000 beyond the Schwarzschild radius of the central SMBH, roughly a 1000 times closer to the central engine than the innermost radius reached by methods based on SD or GD [11]. Although this is still far enough to have significant relativistic effects it is near enough to ensure that the enclosed mass measured is dominated by a SMBH. A disadvantage is that the BLR gas is subject to forces other than gravity; radiation pressure, in particular, is expected to play a significant role in the BLR dynamics. It is therefore very important to demonstrate that reverberation is actually measuring the black hole mass: consistency checks and comparisons with independent methods are needed [10].

Another advantage concerning the RM method is that bright Type 1 AGNs cannot be easily probed using standard techniques, precisely because the bright AGN continuum overwhelms the dynamical signature of the gas and dust needed for resolved dynamical studies [11].

Another advantage is that unlike SMBH masses derived from resolved kinematics, those inferred from RM do not depend on the cosmology adopted.

Because the BLR size is measured directly in physical units from the time delay (equation 3) the **distance to the host galaxy does not enter the analysis**. This means that the redshift to which RM measurements can be pushed is limited only by the requirement that the AGN must be bright enough to be easily detected [11].

4 The iron $K\alpha$ emission line

Most of the radiation from luminous accreting SMBHs is released within the innermost $10r_s$ radii. In such an energetic environment, iron is a major source of X-ray line emission, with strong emission lines in the 6.4 – 6.9 keV band. Observations of such line emission can provide a diagnostic of the accretion flow and the behavior of matter and radiation in the strong gravity regime very close to the SMBH. The rapid X-ray variability found in many Seyfert galaxies is strong evidence for the emission originating at small radii [15].

The ultimate test as to its nature (a SMBH or a dense star cluster?) can only reside in the detection of relativistic velocities within a few Schwarzschild radii. The study of the 6.4 keV Iron Emission $K\alpha$ line allows us to probe the region within a few Schwarzschild radii of the central engine. However its use in deriving SMBH masses is still limited by the resolution of the present day X-ray telescopes [11].

Broad $K\alpha$ line emission seems to be an almost ubiquitous property of the X-ray spectra of Seyfert 1 galaxies, being detected in 80% of cases [11]. The study of fluorescent iron emission strongly suggests that the central regions in Seyfert 1 galaxies are under the influence of the extremely strong gravitational field expected in the presence of a SMBH [11].

The first detection of $K\alpha$ iron emission was made by Exosat in the Seyfert 1 galaxy MCG-6-30-15 [11].

The iron $K\alpha$ line becomes a powerful testbed for the immediate environment around the central SMBH, as well as a unique tool for testing our knowledge of the properties of space and time in very strong gravitational fields. The line profile can not only be used to determine the inclination of the accretion disk but also the spin of the central black hole [11].

The next step in the study of the Iron $K\alpha$ line will require the increase in spectral resolution and collective area afforded by the next generation of X-ray satellites. If the Fe $K\alpha$ line responds to flares in the X-ray continuum produced in the corona above the accretion disk, then the disk structure can be studied using **reverberation mapping** techniques (Section 3) which can potentially lead to a robust measurement of the SMBH mass [11].

5 The $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ scaling relation

There is a remarkably tight correlation between the masses of the central SMBHs in galaxies and the velocity dispersion σ of the stars in the bulge component [10, 11]:

$$M_{\bullet} \approx 1.66 \times 10^8 M_{\odot} \left(\frac{\sigma}{200 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right)^{4.86} \quad (7)$$

This correlation was initially established on the basis of quiescent galaxies, although the maser source NGC 4258 was also included. Subsequently it was shown that some AGNs with both, RM mass estimates and published stellar velocity dispersions showed consistency with the $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ relationship [10].

SMBH masses measured through GD, SD and MD are tightly connected to the velocity dispersion of the host bulge, such that the $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ relation can be used to estimate SMBH masses with at least 30% accuracy from a single measurement of σ [11].

Gebhardt et al. (2000) [16] presented tantalizing evidence that AGNs might follow the same $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ relation as quiescent galaxies. Ferrarese et al. (2001) [17] started a systematic program to map all reverberation mapped AGNs onto the $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ plane. The remarkable agreement between SMBH masses measured in AGNs and quiescent galaxies with similar velocity dispersion is strong observational support for the reliability of the AGN masses. These studies promise to shed light on the value of the geometric factor f [11].

The $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ relation allows one to infer SMBH masses with 30% accuracy from a single measurement of the large scale bulge velocity dispersion. Through σ , it has therefore become possible to explore the role played by the SMBH mass in driving the character of the nuclear activity, not only in individual galaxies, but also in different classes of AGNs. Studies of SMBH demographics, both in quiescent and active galaxies have relied heavily on the relation [11]. Based on the scatter around the AGN $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ relationship, reverberation masses seem to be accurate to about a factor of three, with the largest systematic source of uncertainty probably being the inclination of the BLR [10].

On the case of AGNs with high redshift the relation given by equation (7) must be replaced by [18]:

$$\log \frac{M_{\bullet}}{M_{\odot}} \approx 8.13 + 4.02 \log \left(\frac{\sigma}{200 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right) - 0.138 \log(1 + z) \quad (8)$$

6 List of SMBHs

On Table 1 we show a list of 101 SMBHs. In each case it is shown besides the respective mass, the method by which the mass was determined (although in some cases the mass has been determined by more than one method), the redshift and the kind of object (according to SIMBAD).

It is not a complete and exhaustive list. However, the list aims to give an idea of the state of the art about the number of SMBHs already known and about the methods that were used to identify them and to determine their masses. In terms of observation methods, the 101 SMBHs are distributed as follows:

- (1) SPM - Stellar Proper Motion (Section 2)
- (29) SD - Stellar Dynamics (Section 2)
- (16) GD - ionized Gas Dynamics (Section 2)
- (2) CO - molecular CO rotation curve dynamics [12]
- (9) MD - Maser Dynamics (Section 2)
- (17) RM - Reverberation Mapping (Section 3)
- (3) Fe K band - Iron $K\alpha$ emission line (Section 4)
- (10) $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ scaling relation (Section 5)
- (3) $M_{\bullet} - M_{spheroid}$ scaling relation [19, 20]
- (3) Spectroscopy
- (6) BBH - Binary Black Hole Dynamics
- (1) Stellar tidal disruption
- (1) jet power - accretion rate relation

7 Discussion and conclusions

It is now well established that SMBHs are present at the centre of many galaxies including our own galaxy. The masses of such SMBHs have been measured, by different methods (see Section 2 to 5 and Table 1), in nearby galaxies as well as in distant quasars.

Table 1: A list of 101 SMBHs: **(1)** Name, **(2)** King of object according to SIMBAD, **(3)** mass of the SMBH, **(4)** observation method (see text and references for more details), **(5)** redshift, **(6)** references.

SMBH	Kind of object	$\log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right)$	Observation method	z	Ref.
2QZJ002830	QSO	9.7	RM	2.403	[21]
M32 / NGC 0221	Interacting Galaxies, cE2 AGN	6.4	SD	-0.000667	[12]
M31 / NGC 224	Interacting Galaxies, SA(s)b	8.2	SD	-0.001	[12]
UGC 00542	Sb, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.1	$M_{\bullet}/M_{spheroid}$	0.0150	[22]
NGC 0317A	S0, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.3	$M_{\bullet}/M_{spheroid}$	0.01766	[22]
UGC 00670	Galaxy, SBb?	8.4	$M_{\bullet}/M_{spheroid}$	0.01595	[22]
NGC 0821	Galaxy with classical bulge, E6	8.2	SD	0.00579	[12]
3C66B/UGC 1841	E, Seyfert 1 Galaxy	8.5	GD	0.02126	[23]
NGC 1023	SB0, Interacting Galaxies	7.6	SD	0.00213	[23]
M77 / NGC 1068	Sb, Sy 2, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	6.9	MD	0.00379	[23]
NGC 1097	SBb(s), LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.1	CO	0.00424	[23]
3C75 / NGC 1128	Pair of Galaxies	8.4	BBH	0.02315	[24]
NGC 1194	Seyfert 2 Galaxy, SA0	7.9	MD	0.01360	[23]
NGC 1316	SAB, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.2	SD	0.00587	[23]
HB890329-385	QSO	9.8	RM	2.433	[27]
4C 37.11	Seyfert Galaxy	10.2	BBH	0.05505	[28]
NGC 1417	Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	7.6	M- σ	0.013801	[26]
3C120	S0, LPQ, BLRG Sy1, Seyfert 1 Galaxy	7.7	RM	0.03301	[23]
HE0450-2958	Seyfert 1 Galaxy	8.9	BBH	0.28581	[43]
PKS 0521-365	BL Lac	8.52	M- σ	0.05655	[45]
PKS 0548-322	blazar, BL Lac	8.2	M- σ	0.06900	[45]
NGC 2273	Seyfert 2, SB(r)a	6.9	MD	0.00614	[23]
EXO 0706.1+5913	BL Lac	8.3	M- σ	0.12500	[45]
APM 08279+5255	Quasar	10.4	RM	3.91220	[34]

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Table 1 (continued).

SMBH	Kind of object	$\log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right)$	Observation method	z	Ref.
OJ287 (a)	BL Lac	10.3	BBH	0.306	[46]
OJ287 (b)	BL Lac	8.1	BBH	0.306	[46]
NGC 2778	E, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	7.2	SD	0.00683	[23]
NGC 2787	SB0, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	7.6	GD	0.00232	[23]
SDSS J090033.50+421547.0	Quasar	9.6	spectroscopy	3.290	[48]
MCG 5-23-16	LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	7.7	Fe K band	0.04252	[33]
NGC 2960	LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	7.0	MD	0.71303	[23]
SDSS J094202.04+042244.5	Quasar	9.7	spectroscopy	3.276	[48]
M81 / NGC 3031	Sb, Seyfert 2	7.8	GD	-0.00011	[23]
NGC 3079	SB, Seyfert 2 Galaxy	6.4	MD	0.00372	[23]
NGC 3115	S0, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	9.0	SD	0.00221	[23]
NGC 3245	SA0, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.3	GD	0.00442	[23]
NGC 3377	E5, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.3	SD	0.00222	[23]
NGC 3379 / M105	E1, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.6	SD	0.00304	[23]
NGC 3384	SB0, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	7.0	SD	0.00235	[23]
Mrk 421	BL Lac	8.2	M- σ	0.03002	[44, 45]
NGC 3516	Seyfert 1, SB	7.4	RM	0.33995	[23]
NGC 3608	E2, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.7	SD	0.00409	[23]
Mrk 180	BL Lac	8.2	M- σ	0.04528	[45]
NGC 3862	Quasar, E	8.4	GD	0.00884	[23]
NGC 3783	Seyfert 1 Galaxy	7.5	RM	0.009755	[26]
NGC 3998	SA0, Seyfert	8.9	SD	0.00350	[23]
NGC 4062	Emission-line galaxy	6.6	RM	0.002536	[26]
NGC 4151	SAB, Seyfert 1	7.8	SD	0.00332	[23]
NGC 4258 / M106	SABbc, Seyfert 2	7.6	MD	0.00149	[23]
NGC 4261	E2-3, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.7	GD	0.00738	[23]

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Table 1 (continued).

SMBH	Kind of object	$\log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right)$	Observation method	z	Ref.
NGC 4291	E3, Candidate AGN, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	9.0	SD	0.00586	[23]
NGC 4350	SA0, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.6	SD	0.00404	[23]
NGC 4342	S0, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.7	SD	0.00254	[23]
NGC 4374 / M84	Seyfert 2, E1, LERG, LINER Sy2	9.0	GD	0.00339	[23]
NGC 4388	Seyfert 2	6.9	MD	0.02403	[23]
NGC 4438	SA(s)0, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	7.9	RM	0.00024	[35]
TON 618	QSO	10.8	RM	2.219	[21]
NGC 4459	SA0, HII Galaxy	7.9	GD	0.00398	[25]
3C 273 / PG 1226+023	BL Lac	8.8	RM	0.00149	[40]
NGC 4473	E5, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.0	SD	0.00749	[23]
NGC 4486B	E0, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.8	SD	0.00519	[23]
NGC 4486 / M87	E+0-1 pec, NLRG Sy:Brightest galaxy in a Cluster	9.6	GD	0.00428	[23]
NGC 4589	E2 LINER, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.6	RM	0.00660	[35]
NGC 4564	E6, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.0	SD	0.00381	[23]
NGC 4579	SAB, Seyfert	8.0	GD	0.00506	[23]
NGC 4596	SB0, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.0	GD	0.00631	[23]
NGC 4594	Sa, Sy1.9, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.8	SD	0.00342	[23]
RX J1242.6-1119A	Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.3	star tidal disruption	0.00842	[42]
NGC 4649 / M60	Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies, E2	9.7	SD	0.0037	[32]
NGC 4697	E6, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.3	SD	0.00414	[23]
NGC 4742	E4, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	7.1	SD	0.00424	[23]
NGC 4751	Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	9.4	SD	0.006511	[12]
NGC 4945	SB _j , Seyfert 2 Galaxy	6.1	MD	0.00188	[23]
NGC 5033	SA, Seyfert 1	7.2	M- σ	0.00292	[26]
NGC 5128 / Centaurus A	Seyfert 2 Galaxy, S0	7.8	SD	0.00183	[23]

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Table 1 (continued).

SMBH	Kind of object	$\log\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right)$	Observation method	z	Ref.
NGC 5194 / M51	SA, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	6.0	GD	0.00154	[23]
MCG-6-30-15	E-S0 Seyfert 1	7.3	Fe K band	0.00775	[36, 37]
NGC 5490	Radio Galaxy	8.7	GD	0.016575	[23]
NGC 5495	Seyfert 2 Galaxy	7.0	MD	0.022456	[23]
NGC 5548	(R')SA(s)0/a Sy1.5, Seyfert 1 Galaxy	7.8	RM	0.01717	[26]
NGC 5838	SA0- LINER, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	8.6	RM	0.00447	[35]
NGC 5845	E, Galaxy in Group of Galaxies	8.7	SD	0.00491	[29]
AP Lib / J1517.7-2421	BL Lac	8.1	jet power - accretion	0.04903	[38]
Arp 220 / IC 4553	Seyfert Galaxy	8.9	CO	0.01840	[47]
SDSS J173352.23+540030.4	Quasar	9.5	spectroscopy	3.432	[48]
NGC 6251	E, Seyfert 2 Galaxy	8.8	GD	0.02471	[30]
Mrk 501	BL Lac , E?	8.2	BBH	0.03366	[39]
Milky Way	X-ray source, Sbc, PofG	6.6	SPM	–	[12]
NGC 6500	SAab, LINER-type Active Galaxy Nucleus	8.6	GD	0.01001	[41]
3C 371	BL Lac	8.5	M- σ	0.05100	[45]
NGC 6814	Seyfert 1 Galaxy	7.0	RM	0.005227	[23]
NGC 7052	E, Radio Galaxy	8.6	GD	0.01558	[31]
2QZJ214355	QSO	9.8	RM	2.62	[27]
PKS 2201+044	Seyfert 1 Galaxy	7.8	M- σ	0.02700	[45]
2QZJ221516	QSO	9.2	RM	2.706	[27]
NGC 7314	Seyfert 1, SAB	6.7	Fe K band	0.00476	[33]
NGC 7332	Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	7.1	SD	0.00399	[23]
2QZJ224743	QSO	10.2	RM	2.59	[27]
IC 1459	E3 LINER, Galaxy in Pair of Galaxies	9.4	SD	0.00601	[25]
NGC 7457	SA0, Galaxy	7.0	SD	0.00281	[29]
1ES 2344+514	BL Lac	8.7	M- σ	0.00476	[45]

In this work we have selected a sample of 101 SMBHs. In this sample, we have included mainly SMBHs for which the mass was determined by dynamical methods (SPM, SD, GD, CO and MD). This corresponds to 57 out of the 101 SMBHs.

In order to emphasize the importance of the scaling relation we have also included in our sample 13 SMBHs for which the masses were determined with the help of the $M_{\bullet} - \sigma$ and $M_{\bullet} - M_{spheroid}$ scaling relations.

We have also included 17 SMBHs for which the mass was obtained with the RM method which is particularly useful in the case of distant AGNs.

Considering that there are a crescent number of binary SMBHs candidates (mainly resulting from galaxy merging) we have also included a few examples in our list.

Depending on each SMBH and on the observation method used, we may be probing an area that may be more or less close to the events horizon (which is given by the Schwarzschild radius, r_s). Typically the values can vary between $3r_s$ (Fe K band) to $\sim 10^6 r_s$ (GD and SD). The closer we get to the event horizon, the stronger the hypothesis that the object is actually a SMBH. The next step is to determine the radius of influence for each one of the 101 SMBHs and to compare these radii with the respective r_s .

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